

Skills 4 eosc

Skills4EOSC Virtual Round Tables Report

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Abstract

The Skills4EOSC project is dedicated to establish a training ecosystem for Open Science and FAIR principles, fostering a skilled workforce for EOSC. With 44 partners across 18 European countries, alignment on our vision is crucial. We've introduced Interactive Virtual Roundtables (VRTs) as a guided discussion space to ensure alignment, bridge potential gaps in workflows, and enhance our collective understanding. These VRTs go beyond standard project activities, facilitating meaningful engagement among partners. This document outlines the methodology of VRTs and presents the results achieved through these interactive discussions.

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Introduction

The Skills4EOSC project is focused on building a training ecosystem for Open Science and FAIR principles to equip a skilled workforce for EOSC. With 44 partners spanning 18 European countries, maintaining alignment on our shared vision is strategically essential. To facilitate this alignment, we have introduced Interactive Virtual Roundtables (VRTs), which transcend typical project activities. These VRTs serve as guided discussion spaces, aimed at achieving alignment among partners while identifying and addressing potential workflow gaps and enhancing mutual understanding.

This document outlines the VRT methodology and presents the outcomes achieved through these interactive discussions.

1.2 The role of VRTs in advancing alignment and collaboration

The VRT is an activity/space developed to raise awareness and strategic alignment with the project partners. This is an activity that goes beyond the usual project activities. It acts as a guided discussion; thus, the aim is to seek for alignment, but also aims to identify and address potential gaps in existing work flows and to enhance common understanding. Furthermore, the VRT also opened space for initiate the adoption of corrective measures whenever there is a demand or a need, such the adoption on a central concept in order to generate conceptual alignment between the WPs or foster knowledge transfer inside of the consortium. The VRTs has proven to be a suitable instrument for carrying out these tasks. With these VRTs the project is enhancing: a) Cohesion; b) Alignment of knowledge and experience; c) Bottom-up processing and feedback; d) Community building; e) Foster the extended competencies of the consortium beyond project objectives; f) Address transversal activities beyond project objectives.

1.2.1 VRT Methodology

The organisation of VRT is based on the selection of a central theme and of sub-topics, defined together with the Coordinator of the project, to serve as a point of reference and for better involvement of the participants. The event has a duration of 90 minutes, the first 35 minutes are dedicated to the presentation of the agenda, theme and sub-themes, followed by a brief presentation (by the organiser or guest) on the chosen theme. The other 55 minutes are dedicated to the guided discussion, where the participants are encouraged to participate by the moderator and the discussion topic is not restricted to the topic that was presented. A link is also shared with participants in advance for collective note-taking. All participants will have one more working day after the event to edit and/or add remarks and comments. Based on the minutes and what has been presented and discussed this document has been created.

2 to 3 slides are shared previously with the participants and whenever possible accompanied by some questions for reflection, however the discussion will not be limited to the proposed theme or questions. All issues raised and necessary feedback to ensure the best development of the project will be addressed at the General Assembly meetings and/or Plenary meetings.

1.3 Summary of First-Year VRTs

Throughout the project's first year, we successfully organized two VRTs, with the participation of at least one representative from each consortium member, along with the active involvement of all task leaders and members. TU Wien played a key role in orchestrating partner engagement during this period.

VRTs	Focus	Key Takeaway message
1st VRT: Sustainable development and community building among	The aim was to raise awareness and sensitize the partners that the project leads to a process: <i>Start thinking about it from the end.</i> And also, on reflecting	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Broaden the Open Science concept. 2. Adapt Competence Centres (CCs) to

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<p>the partners of the Skills4EOSC project <i>(31st March 2023)</i></p>	<p>on what actions are possible to take now in order to be successful after the project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A summarised introduction to the concept of Skills4EOSC Competence Centre's nodes (CCs) and Competence Center's Network (CCnet) <i>(Emma Lazzeri, GARR)</i> • A short presentation "Project-oriented thinking to process-oriented thinking" <i>(Paolo Budroni, TUW)</i> 	<p>regional contexts.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Tailor training materials to target groups. 4. Emphasize sustainability and community involvement.
<p>2nd VRT: Definitions of Open Science in relation to Skills4EOSC <i>(12th June 2023)</i></p>	<p>The aim was to provide strategic alignment in the chosen definition of Open Science with the project partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence Centres according to the vision of the Project <i>(Emma Lazzeri, GARR)</i> • Open Science: the need for curricula <i>(Eva Mendez, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)</i> • About Open Science <i>(Kevin Ashley, DCC)</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open Science varies by discipline. 2. Three core elements: knowledge access, reproducibility, and infrastructure. 3. Context-sensitive Open Science definitions work best. 4. Focus on practical actions, not rigid definitions. 5. Policies are essential for unifying diverse definitions. 6. UNESCO's comprehensive definition is suggested.

2 Appendix

In the appendix, are reported a summary of the discussions and key takeaways from the two VRTs held during the first year. The first VRT took place on March 31, 2023, with a focus on "Sustainable Development and Community Building among the Partners of the Skills4EOSC Project," while the second VRT occurred on June 12, 2023, addressing "Definitions of Open Science in Relation to Skills4EOSC."

2.1 1st Skills4EOSC VRT

Activity	Skills4EOSC the first Interactive Virtual Roundtable (T1.2.2)
Theme	Sustainable development and community building among the partners of Skills4EOSC project
Date	31 st March 2023, 11:00-12:30 CET, Zoom
Organiser	Paolo Budroni and Juliana Giroletti, TU Wien
Co-organiser	Emma Lazzeri and Sara Di Giorgio, GARR
Speakers	Paolo Budroni (TU Wien) and Emma Lazzeri (GARR)
Authors	Juliana Giroletti (TUW) and Paolo Budroni (TUW)
Contributors	Nida siddiqui-van Leersum and Sonja Filiposka (UKIM)

The Skills4EOSC Project Advance Open Science skills by unifying the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem, closing the three gaps Identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda in relation to Open Science competences concerning skills and training: a lack of **Open Science and data expertise**, a lack of clearly defined data **professional profiles and career paths for these roles**, and fragmentation in training resources.

On 31 March 2023, the first Skills4EOSC Virtual Roundtable (VRT) was held aiming to provide strategic alignment with the project partners. This is an activity that goes beyond the usual project activities. It acts as a guided discussion; thus, the aim is to seek for alignment, but also aims to identify

and address potential gaps in existing work flows and to enhance alignments. The first topic chosen for this activity was Sustainable development and community building among the partners of the Skills4EOSC project.

As an introduction to the chosen topic, Emma Lazzeri summarised the concept of Skills4EOSC Competence Centre’s nodes (CCs) and Competence Center’s Network (CCnet) previously presented at the Plenary meeting (17 March 2023). She emphasised that the overall aim of our project is to indeed to build a Coordination Network of Competence Centers for Open Science, FAIR and EOSC in the countries covered by the Skills4EOSC project and beyond. Furthermore, she reflected on what could happen after the project. Start, perhaps, to design actions that might be needed after the project. At the same time, she suggested focusing on reflecting on what actions are possible to take now in order to be successful after the project. One of the possible actions would be for each member to start thinking about becoming one of those people who will possess the competencies presented previously that will be transferred during the project and to connect to their local network. This is very important, because we need to build something for their local community and include the community in the co-creation of the CCs.

The participants present were furthermore encouraged by Paolo Budroni to shift the focus from "**project-oriented thinking to process-oriented thinking**". In this sense, the project context could be seen as a big river, in which the boats sailing on the river represent all projects, including Skills4EOSC (see figure 01).

Figure 01: Skills4EOSC is paving the way for the creation of National CCs in all regions. The project is taking care of embedding all related project in this process

All these projects are in the process of building the EOSC, which is related to the federations of yet existing services and infrastructure for a web of FAIR data and services in Europe, which is EOSC. What is stressed is that it would be ideal to start thinking from the end. The Skills4EOSC project will have an end and it is embedded in the process of building the EOSC, in which our boats are sailing towards the CCs. This is the main topic; how we can now reflect on changing attitudes and changing point of view thinking from project to processing order to build the CCs. we are aiming to have at least 27 CCs. So, **from project to process**. What does this mean? There are some key concept CCs nodes, CCs network, Minimum Viable Skillset, Training of Trainers (ToT), Master Trainer, Professional Networks, User support network, Co-creation mechanism.

As regards the concepts and the objective of the project presented, additionally to the preposition of changing the focus to reflect from a process perspective, the main issues presented by the participants were grouped by theme and presented below:

Open Science: Open Science concept is wider than Open Access/Open Data, it should consider the whole flow of research, including the activities to produce the scientific results. We need to iterate the concept of Open Science to be closer to our communities. Proposed action points and reflection:

- Different points of view concerning the definition of Open Science (UNESCO definition vs definition of eight pillars of open science offered by the EC)
- To reflect on whether there is a need to align the adopted concept of Open Science with the EOSC definition as adopted by the EOSC Association
- Note for reference that the SRIA (p.21) uses the FOSTER project scope of Open Science
- Review the sources adopted in the project to date and perhaps harmonise them within the project scope

Figure 1.3: Research lifecycle and Open Science (from the FOSTER project)

Figure O2: Scope of Open Science adopted by FOSTER project (source: SRIA p.21)

Competence Centres (CCs): the reality of CCs varies between European countries. In some cases, it will be only one organisation that will do this and in another, you will need to bring together several actors to create this network. Proposed action points and reflection:

- Our goal of building a CC in each country should also include the possibility of linking existing CCs, including RIs
- Consider that a CC may be constituted by several organizations and consider more than one member in the discussions and co-creation processes
- "No institute can fulfil the role of the CC": can the CC fulfil the role as a clearing point?

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- Consider the point of view of European (EU) institutions, and the point of view on non-EU institutions: what kind of impact could it have on the creation of Open Centres of Scientific Competence?
- Reflect on how to align what we would like to see beyond the project versus with what perhaps the different CCs have as their own ambitions?

Training: We are focusing more to spread the knowledge that is needed for general Open Science and FAIR and of course these is related to up taken of EOSC and with the fact we can interact with EOSC. Proposed action points and reflection:

- In the communication and training actions to be carried out in the project it is important to reiterate that talking about Open Science is not the same as talking about open data and open access
- We need to understand how many ToT we have to perform and what kind of learning materials we need to set up, customised for each target group. Do we need to customised the materials?
- In the project proposal of Skills4EOSC there were three gaps in the SRIA, which were identified: are they still of relevance for the project?
- To have a common framework, so that when starting to elaborate the material we have a basis of comparison to add value and save time in the elaboration of these materials

Sustainability: three aspects were raised on sustainability. First, the need to properly use resources to avoid overlapping activities. Second, to achieve project sustainability it is necessary to involve the community and develop trainers to continue the work after the end of the project. Third, regarding the importance of the funding mechanisms of the CCs. An additional reflection made is that we are working in institutions that are notably committed to OS, committed to Open Access, thus we are committed through our links with the institutions we represent. So, part of sustainable development is ensured by our affiliations. Proposed action points and reflection:

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- OS is a shift of mentality. So how can we ensure this shift of mentality? How can we encourage colleagues for this shift of mentality?
- For further reflections: do we need a mapping of activities? (overview); how can we avoid overlapping's; how can we improve interactions between WPs
- What needs to be shared in the project: "commons"?
- Reflect on whether there is any overlap in the collection of materials between WPs.
- The project is experiencing "different chronologies in the WPs". Is it needed a monitoring and alignment action?

Further reflections

- 'Learning pathway' is another term where it may be useful to have a shared understanding/definition, both about what it means and what is the general corpus through which we have a pathway
- The legal aspect of the EOSC is strictly constructed within the frameworks of European laws
- How to embed the national events within the project, considering that we are now thinking from a process perspective rather than a project perspective. Is there a need for repetition of events?

Final remarks. Broad definitions are useful in describing to people what Open Science actually means. Besides, it is clear that no single institution will have to define Open Science on its own, but in the project, we have the challenge to provide clarification, even though our training in general may focus on a narrower set of topics. Additionally, our project has the mission to fill the three gaps in SRIA. To this end, starting with clear definitions - rather than having moving targets - is key to having sustainable development.

2.2 2nd Skills4EOSC VRT

Activity	Skills4EOSC the first Interactive Virtual Roundtable (T1.2.2)
Theme	Definitions of Open Science in relation to Skills4EOSC
Date	12th June 2023, 11:00-12:30 CET, Zoom
Organiser	Paolo Budroni and Juliana Giroletti, TU Wien
Co-organiser	Emma Lazzeri and Sara Di Giorgio, GARR
Moderator	Paolo Budroni (TU Wien)
Speakers	Emma Lazzeri (GARR), Eva Mendez (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid), Kevin Ashley (DCC)
Authors	Juliana Giroletti (TUW) and Paolo Budroni (TUW)

The Second Virtual Roundtable (VRT) was dedicated to reflections on the **definitions of Open Sciences (OS)** in the context of the project the Skills4EOSC. The moderator started with the statement that the idea of OS is a wide field, of actions, of ideas, of concepts and of definitions. Given the fact that according to project proposal one of the main objectives is to stimulate the creation of Competence Centers (CC), it is essential to clarify:

- which definition of Open Sciences could be used in the project, in other words,
- which definition of OS will be used for the creation of a CC, as well as
- which definition of OS will be used for the development of the other objectives of the project, such as:
 - what are the minimum viable skills required by the most diverse actors regarding the implementation and practice of OS or
 - what does an OS ready institution mean or
 - what is an OS compatible practice or
 - what are the OS essentials?

The moderator also emphasised that, in order to find key competences to enable OS practices, it is necessary to have adequate knowledge of standards, applications, tools and best practices for delivering, managing,

reusing, sharing, and analysing FAIR data as well as other Digital Research Objects.

Still in the context of the project and in the introduction of the VRT, the project coordinator highlighted that the adopted definition of CC is something that already exists and is being used in similar initiatives and European projects, as for instance in the ENRIO Network and Semiconductors. The definition of CCs in the context of the Skills4EOSC project focuses on some specific elements: Open Science, FAIR principles in relation to research outputs, Research Data Management and EOSC in general. It was also stated, that the **Competence Centre Network (CCNet) should be based on diversity at local level**. In this way, each CC may have its own structure, operational model and organisation, but the project tries to foster the network as a mean of harmonisation and alignment.

The first speaker, Eva Mendes (leader of WP4, which mainly aims to create curricula and learning pathways for Open Science ready institutions), reflected on the different contexts of OS (OS Umbrella and its variation, the OS Mushroom, Open Scholarship, Open Knowledge and the OS Parachute) by presenting a variation of graphics with definitions of Open Science used in different contexts. From the context of the Skills4EOSC project, Eva Mendes mentioned that **the UNESCO definition of OS seems to be “technically perfect”**: OS is not just a movement; it is a construct. It is a construct that puts many things on the table, such as: the economic benefits, the quality and integrity of research, the global benefits of research, public disclosure and engagement, innovation as a valorisation of knowledge and efficiency. These are the main values that we should address when teaching Open Science from a technical point of view and from a social point of view. However, Eva Mendes emphasized that if Science is not open (parachute analogy), it will not help us (“like a closed parachute”). OS and open knowledge accelerate research and advancement to face societal challenges like pandemics or the realization of the UN-SDGs.

Eva Mendes also reflected on the challenges identified at the project kick-off meeting and highlighted some aspects of the identified challenges. First, the

importance of having a **glossary** to achieve a common understanding of the concepts (such as: "OS essentials", "OS Ecosystem", " OS ready institutions", "Competence Centers", etc.). Second, the relevance of **identifying who are the "trainers and trainees", who are the target group**, in order to understand the dimension of their different feelings towards OS and knowledge. Third, the **OS curriculum and the EOSC at all levels**. Last but not least, the target of the project is to foster educational skills and always consider the aims of OS (going beyond EOSC).

Characters from the movie Inside Out (left to right): Sadness, Fear, Anger, Disgust, and Joy. (Disney Wiki)

As important as understanding the different OS contexts, it is also important to identify the diversity of feelings of the target audience towards it. It was also mentioned that it is necessary to combine all these feelings and aims and focus on the last feeling (Yay!), which is “people are

happy/open to learn”. Target groups are not only “the research community itself”, but “researchers at different degrees or different layers of the research career”, such as undergraduate students, PhD students as well as Data Stewards and Data Professionals (nota bene: there are many professions that can be addressed, like as data librarians and curators, legal and ethical expert roles, data analytics, data analysts and other data-related professions). Therefore, it is essential to define the " *Open Science essentials*" to be then included in undergraduate and PhD courses in order to support professionals.

All the **stakeholders** being addressed in WP4 are: University and Research Performing Organizations; Research libraries; Research services (support services for OS) and E-Infrastructures in the context of EOSC; Policy Making Organizations and all Researchers as such.

The second speaker, Kevin Ashley (DCC), started his presentation by reflecting on the language issue and the relationship with the audience. He pointed out that, depending on the idiom or the audience, it is sometimes better to use the term '**Open Research**' or '**Open Scholarship**'. Those terms are to be considered as equivalent. Also, in some European languages there is no difference when you try to translate them. So rather than focusing on pinpointing a chosen definition of OS, in the project Skills4EOsc we should accept the ambiguity that results from working with more than one concept. Therefore, Kevin Ashley reflected on the various definitions of OS and focuses on how they can all be useful.

Amidst the many existing definitions, it is relevant to wonder what do all these definitions of Open Science describe? For this reflection, a brief presentation of OS definitions was given (OECD, Openscienceasap.org, UNESCO, FOSTER project and European Commission). Among the definitions presented, it was highlighted that there are **definitions where the focus is on action/measures, on describing what needs to be done to practice Open Science**: what does the researcher need to do? what do the people who support the researcher need to do? what do the organisations they work for, the university, private companies, etc. need to do? And there are definitions where the focus is on the effects of results/ambitions. In a way, the definitions are trying to justify that OS is a good thing (the need for open practices). Another aspect to consider is the high receptivity when the concept is reduced to a small number of key ideas: '8 pillars' or '4 principles' and so forth. And each of these definitions will talk the key ideas as if they were the most important thing. They are all equally true and there is no universal way to do it.

Before moving to the conclusion of his presentation, Kevin pointed out that UNESCO's definition of OS focuses not on *what* needs to be done, but *why* it needs to be done and the benefits that will result from practicing OS. This definition can be useful for many organisations because the outcomes are very easy to align with mission and its purpose. And, this can justify why an organisation would want to work in an open way.

He concluded the presentation questioning **"what really matters?"** One relevant aspect that needs to be considered is the audience. Depending on the audience, we might need to focus on actions (what does Open Science mean to us? What do we need to do to practice Open Science?) and/or, in other cases, we should focus on results (why is this important? Why should your organization or your group of researchers change the way they work?) It is also important to take a wider view: to think about and encompass data, methods, software, skills, publications and not to limit yourself to a specific area. It is important to stress benefits can help convince those who are unsure. It is also worth mentioning again that Open Science is not open data, and the FAIR principles help to make this clear. Moreover, he emphasises that, above all, most of all these definitions do not assign specific responsibilities to any one actor. Instead, policies (from funders, organisations) usually give the next steps. Policies define, for something to happen, who should do what.

Discussion.

After an extensive and in-depth presentation around Open Science definitions, the principal questions, reflections and remarks made by participants are presented below:

- **OS is also related to non-Open Science.** There is no OS without the recognition of non-Open Science. And between Open Science and Non-Open Science, there are intermediaries (not only commercial ones, but also other kinds of intermediaries, like Competence Centers).
- **When we talk about OS, we are really talking about Open Sciences.** There are several scientific disciplines with very different needs.
- Three main points that are essential for OS have been identified:
 - **Access to knowledge:** important for both researchers and citizens.
 - **Reproducibility:** this important for researchers. With the diversity of disciplines, reproducibility within each field varies and you can identify/define a minimum set of skills needed for science to be reproducible and from there you can improve with more skills and the OS ideal for that field.

- **Access to infrastructure** (the instrument itself): which enables and empowers publications, making possible OS.
- It is likely that there is **no need for a single definition of OS**, but rather a definition that needs to be context sensitive.
- Consider whether the definition of OS needs to be global or localized according to the regions/target audience to work with.
- **Importance of understanding the audience and their context:** If we are dealing with an audience that needs to be persuaded about the relevance of OS, then the focus is on the benefits and the definitions that stress the benefits. If we are working with an audience that is ready and that somehow believes in the importance of the definition of OS, we focus on actions, best practices, tools, etc.
- There is a difference between sticking to a definition and using a definition as a starting point. Different definitions do not always work for all subjects and disciplines.
- There is one advantage if the definitions are not generally, theoretically formulated, but containing starting points for actions that really can be put into practices. If the definitions are too broad, too general, it is difficult to build up a policy on the definitions that works in reality. *It is suggested to use definitions that include starting points for concrete actions that make it easier to link policies to them.*
- **The need to treat the definition of OS without dogmatism.** On the other hand, there is the need to identify or point to something that works as a glue between the different definitions of OS. *It is perceived that this "glue" can be represented by Policies.* Policies rather than definitions, in other words. A good policy behind the grammar of the definitions we will choose can be helpful.
- **It was considered that in case of needing a definition of OS it is recommended to use UNESCO's definition**, which is comprehensive enough and also has a global flavour.
- **About the "OS ready institution":** the OS ready institution has an OS Policy. The context, an institution also means that there is a country that

supports and encourages this practice or not. In this sense, there will exist variations between countries.

- Among WPs, we will need to target the same definitions, the same trainers and trainees, the same skill set, etc. The starting point is thinking what OS is. The next steps are: to think about what is an OS ready institution; what is an OS compliant practice; What is reproducibility.

As final remarks: which kind of approach/responsibility is considered to be adopted when talking about Open Science (actions, measures, results or ambitions)? What kind of responsibilities are being considered when deciding on one or more definitions?

In this category of reflections, we also have to consider the OS essentials that we need to choose. It is important to stress that it is a choice and not an imposed choice. The OS essentials that are chosen will be then transmitted to the CCs. ***In this sense, the CCs can be seen as something that has an intermediary role.*** Still needs to decide between what, but the role is to be an intermediary. In that intermediary role, we have some instruments, like offering support and advice. In this context we can decide what kind of policies will be chosen. And then define what kind of measures and actions you want to start according to the common understanding of the concepts to be achieved in the first category. At that point, it will be possible to choose who will be the instructors we are examining and who will be the recipients.